

"A Study On Job Satisfaction Of Employees In An Organization"

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ABSTRACT

This paper analyse the extent of job satisfaction among workers of ansec human resource services Pvt ltd with the thought of gender, age and skill variations. Job satisfaction is one in every of the key factors that shows the emotions relating to the character of their work. totally different style of studies are conducted to seek out out the factors that confirm job satisfaction and therefore the means it impact productivity within the organization. Job satisfaction will be influenced by a numerous factors e.g. relationship with their supervisor, physical conditions during which the worker works, level of fulfillment in their work etc. increasing geographical point happiness will be a way to realize the specified structure outcome, since happier worker tend to possess the next job performance, a far better communication with colleagues. unitedly with Ansec Human Resource Services pvt ltd, a form survey was delivered to ansec human resource services to spot the extent of satisfaction .

Keywords: Job Satisfaction, Human Resource Management, Convenience Sampling

1. INTRODUCTION

Job satisfaction is one among the necessary a part of the structure behaviour and the practices of the Human Resource Management. It shows the perception of the staff towards their job & commitment to the a company. Job satisfaction primarily deals with the sensation or approach of workers towards their work.

Job satisfaction is principally refers to a person's or individual's feeling of satisfaction on the geographical point, that act as a motivation to figure. it's not self motivation, self state of happiness or satisfaction or happiness however satisfaction of job. Job satisfaction is coupled to the motivation, productivity, absence, mental condition and general life satisfaction. Job

satisfaction is an integral part of the structure work surroundings and important in management worker relationship. Job satisfaction is that the major part of a company as a result of whole progress depends on workers work, if they're not happy with their work then organization can fail to attain their goal.

Competition is obtaining harder day by day and for extant during this competition, the essential part of organization is worker. If workers don't seem to be stable then company's performance won't stable. If workers don't seem to be stable then they'll switch the corporate to different company and will be share our secrets or strategy to different company. this may be terribly dangerous to our company and to avoid this all ought to perceive is workers expectation from the corporate and to grasp whether or not they happy with their work or not.

This study can useful to grasp the approach of worker in a company. In literature, the term Job Satisfaction is employed for individual's perception or people perspective towards the precise side of the entire work scenario at geographical point. The word job indicates a obligation or specific task wherever because the term job satisfaction is of upper orders wherever it's basically associated with human wants and their accomplishment through work. it's generated by the perspective of the person that is completely depends on themselves however well his/her job satisfies his/her numerous demand. it's usually aforementioned that "A happy worker may be a productive worker." Job satisfaction is extremely necessary as a result of most of the folks pay their major time of their life at their work place. Job satisfaction is directly coupled to lifetime of conjointly owing to satisfaction worker may be a happy and happy employee. A extremely happy worker has higher physical and mental health so that they will work additional sky-high at their work place. money is simply not a necessary issue of job satisfaction, if workers area unit pay their majority time at geographical point, company ought to offer them pay check to satisfy them.

2. JOB SATISFACTION - MEANING AND DEFINITION

Job satisfaction refers to a person's feeling and emotions of satisfaction on the task that play role for a motivation to figure. It is not the complacence, happiness or self-contentment however the satisfaction on the task. analysis employees otherwise delineate the factors contributory the task satisfaction and therefore the job discontentedness. Satisfaction will mean the easy feeling state incidental the attainment by associate degree impulse of its objective.

"Job satisfaction may be a positive emotion ensuing from the appraisal or one's job or job experience" - E. A. Locke

“Job satisfaction is that the quantity of delight or happiness related to employment. If you wish job intensely, you'll experience high job satisfaction. If you dislike your job intensely, you'll experience job-dissatisfaction” - saint. J.DuBrins

“Job satisfaction are going to be outlined because the quantity of overall positive impact or feelings that people have towards their jobs” - Fieldman and Arnold

“Job satisfaction is that the set of favourable or unfavourable feelings with that workers read their work” - Keith Davis and Newstrom

Job satisfaction may be a results of employees' perception of however well their job provides those things that area unit viewed as vital. it's usually recognized within the organizational behaviour field that job satisfaction is that the most significant and regularly studied angle.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Paul E. Spector (1997) provides a transient statement on the findings regarding however worker feels towards their work, including: cultural and gender variations in job satisfaction and private and structure causes; and potential consequences of job satisfaction and discontent. He provides with a) concise and smartly communicatory summary of the appliance, assessment, causes and consequences of job satisfaction. Sophie rowan tree (2008) reveals the way to create our life happy while not ever-changing our career or while not ever-changing manner. She gave sensible and realistic steering on however one can do ideal or best job satisfaction and succeed the obstacles or issues at geographic point that create such a large amount of folks sad at work.

Robert M. Hochheiser (1998) value the that means of the geographic point and planned a straightforward formula for success- Forget the concept that tough work alone results in success and instead concentrate on building smart relationships. He asserts that the most effective thanks to win at work is to know what's required to support the egos of bosses, peers, and subordinates. correct assessment of these wants will then be indirectly related to one's own personal goals and exploited to create important geographic point gains. strategies of determinant necessities square measure given for a range of things, and techniques square measure offered to assist create a number of the worst work things a minimum of marginally higher through networking and private development.

C. J. Cranny, Patricia Cain Smith, Eugène F. Stone (1992) reveals perceiving future chance will really be a lot of motivating than really receiving a lift, obtaining promoted, or being given further responsibilities. Jane Boucher (2004) offers sensible recommendation for up each your perception towards their job and also the job itself. She shows employees the way to deal with keeping their jobs during this troublesome economy.

Chris Stride, Toby D. Wall, Nick Cately (2008) wide used measure scales of Job Satisfaction, Mental and physical Health, Job-related Well-being and structure Commitment, along side benchmarking knowledge for comparison. The benchmarking knowledge is predicated on a sample of virtually sixty,000 respondents from a hundred and fifteen totally different organizations across a large spectrum of industries and occupations.

4. OBJECTIVES

- To understand the worker job satisfaction level in Ansec Human Resource Services Pvt. Ltd.
- To identify the varied factors that determines job satisfaction of the worker.
- To study the impact of job satisfaction on the general growth of the worker additionally as organization.
- To study the varied factors that inspires workers.
- To make necessary recommendation for increasing job satisfaction level of workers.

5. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The following methodology has been employed in this study.

5.1 Type of Research:

5.1.1 Descriptive Research:

Descriptive analysis is outlined as an exploration methodology that describes the characteristics of the population or circumstances that's being studied.

A descriptive study is one during which info is gathered from the cluster of individuals while not ever-changing the environment. Its use to a mass info regarding current state.

It conjointly known as survey analysis that is pointed at characterizing scenario and characteristic alliance among elite variables.

5.2 Convenience Sampling:

In Convenience sampling, sample is taken from the cluster of individuals and it's a kind of non likelihood sampling methodology. it's conjointly referred to as grab sampling, accidental sampling or chance sampling. this sort of sampling is most helpful for pilot testing. it's a kind of non likelihood sampling methodology wherever the sample is taken from a majority of

individuals. this sort of sampling is most helpful for pilot testing, pilot testing may be a conduct an attempt before actual study.

6. DATA COLLECTION

The purpose of analysis was explained to the workers and form were administered to them.

1) PRIMARY DATA: info} is 1st hand information, this information collected from employees, manager etc. by conducting the form having one on one interaction with workers.

SAMPLING SIZE: A survey of one hundred workers operating within the organization provided the info base for this study.

7. LIMITATION

The study undertaken has following limitations

- The employees were busy with their serious work in order that they couldn't provide enough time for the interview.
- Some of the worker has not given any applicable answer to the questions whereas doing survey which can have an effect on the study.
- It was impossible to require a survey at giant scale thanks to shortage of your time and resources.
- Employee had provided the answers in form which cannot correct regardless of their actual feelings.
- Insufficient time cause poor focus al together segments.

8. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

According to Hoppock (1935), job satisfaction is a merger of physiological, psychological and environmental factors that makes a person to confess that, "I am happy at my workplace". It has also been defined as the 'end state of feeling of fulfillment'. It is an important dimension of self-esteem and not morale itself.

8.1 TYPES OF HUMAN RESOURCES

The human resources classified into two types. They are:

8.1.1 External Human Resources

These types of human resources stay outside the structure of the organization and they are of prime strength to the development activities including expansion of the Operations of the undertaking. The examples for such human resources are customers, Shareholders etc.

8.1.2. Internal Human resource

These varieties of human resources keep within the structure of the organization, i.e., the kith and kin at the disposal of the endeavor or otherwise it's the productive capability of the human organization of the firm. The human resources at the disposal of the organization, i.e., the interior human resources may be broadly speaking divided into 3 classes. They are:

- (a) Lower Level
- (b) Middle level
- (c) Top level

8.2 DIMENSIONS TO JOB SATISFACTION

1. Job satisfaction is associated degree emotional response to employment scenario. As such, it can not be seen, it will solely be inferred. It relates to one's feeling towards one's job.
2. Job satisfaction is decided by how ever can outcomes meet the expectations of workers.
3. Job satisfaction and job attitudes square measure usually used indistinguishable.

9.FACTORS OF JOB SATISFACTION

There are unit four sorts of factors that determines the task satisfaction, a unit as follows:

- A. Organizational Factors: It includes salaries and wages, promotion probabilities and company policies.
- B. Work Environmental Factors: It includes supervision, work cluster and dealing condition.
- C. Work Itself: It contains job scope and selection, Lack of autonomy and freedom, Role ambiguity and role conflict, fascinating Work.
- D. Personal Factors: It includes temperament, level of education, age & seniority and tenure.

10. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

Q.1 From how many years have you working

Table No.

Particular	No. of Employees
0-3 years	25
3-5 years	20
5-7 years	20
More that 7 years	35

Graph No.1

INTERPRETATION: Here 35% employees have worked more than 7 yrs as they are more satisfied with the company. 25% employees have worked 3 years, 20% employees have worked more than 3-5 years & 20% employees have worked more than 5-7 years.

Q.2 How is the working environment?

Table No.2

Particular	No. of Employees
Participative	60
Autonomy	5
Positive	15
Negative	20

Graph No.2

INTERPRETATION: According to 60% employees working environment is participative,15% employees working environment is positive, 5% employees working environment is autonomy and rest of 20% employees working environment is negative as they are not satisfied with their job.

Q.3 Are employee in the company satisfied with time?

Table No.3

Particular	No. of Employees
Strongly agree	40
Agree	20
disagree	10
Neutral	20
Strongly Disagree	10

Graph No.3

INTERPRETATION: 40 % Employee are strongly agree and satisfied with the time, 20% are just agree with the time, 10% employees are disagree with it, 20% employees are neutral and 10% employees are strongly disagree.

Q.4 Are you satisfied with your salary?

Table No.4

Particular	No. of Employees
Yes	80
No	20

Graph No.4

INTERPRETATION: 80% Employees are satisfied with their salary and 20% are not satisfied with their salary.

Q.5 Are employee get rewards if the target is accomplished?

Table No.5

Particular	No. of Employees
Strongly agree	40
Agree	20
disagree	10
Neutral	5
Strongly Disagree	25

Graph No.5

INTERPRETATION: 40 % Employees are satisfied with the rewards which is provided by the company for target accomplishment, while 25 % employees are strongly disagree, 20% employees are agree with it ,10 % employees are disagree and 5% are neutral.

11. FINDINGS

1. Employees are free from their tensions and problems related to their family security so they can give more time for their work and family too.

2. They need to give special importance on training and development programmes.
3. Relationships between employee in the organization need to be more supportive so they work effectively.
4. There is free and friendly communication between employees.
5. promotion policies provided by the company should be examine.
6. The grievance handling system of the company is equally favoured and unfavoured by the employees.
7. To create extreme job interest and career opportunity, Job rotation system should be improved to develop various skills in employees.
8. Career development in the company is limited only to energetic, motivated and goal oriented employees for improving their skills.
9. Some of the employees do not have greater involvement in decision-making and some employees are involved in the process of decision making.
10. Employees are highly satisfied with the company as they provide satisfactory medical benefits to the employee.

12. SUGGESTION

- Organization ought to need to build effective common channel.
- Organization ought to give correct safety measures within the organization.
- Organization ought to give correct leave to workers in order that they will pay time with their families and friends.
- Organization ought to give additional occasion to workers so as to participate in deciding.

13. CONCLUSION

- From the analysis I will conclude that the duty at Ansec Human Resources Services Pvt. Ltd provides the chance to the workers to make up his/her skills at the duty.
- In Ansec Human Resources Services Pvt. Ltd they follow the systematic coming up with and review method to investigate the performance of worker. From analysis it absolutely was conjointly found that there's a scope for the development of operating conditions.

- Wage package significantly hike so it may be in par with market rate. Finally i'd wish to conclude that the workers of Ansec Human Resources Services Pvt .Ltd ar glad with their work and organization.

14. REFERENCE

BOOK:

HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT -C.R.KOTHARI

I) WEBSITES :

1.www.ansechr.com

2.www.google.com